

Online Examination System

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Abstract—

A design and application of adaptive online exam system are carried out in this paper. Adaptive exam systems determine different question sets automatically and interactively for each student and measure their competence on a certain area of discipline instead of comparing their gains with each other. Through an adaptive exam technique, a student's distraction and motivation loss that is led by the questions with quite lower hardness level than his/her competency is prevented. In addition, negative effects of questions requiring higher knowledge than his/her competency over a student's self-confidence and morale are dismissed. Since questions are specialized so that they can allow making clear deductions about student gains, they are able to detect student competencies more effectively. Requiring less total time for measuring and being more flexible in the exam management are among the advantages provided by the system. Self sufficiency of the system in terms of planning, repeating and assessment of the measurement process especially allows itself to be used in the individual education sets. Through this system, student competencies can be determined more effectively in cases such as distant-learning, in

which some challenges are experienced frequently.

Keywords: Adaptive exam systems, expert systems, online exam, individualized learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Online Examination are used to evaluate the Student's knowledge using modern computer technology without any effect on the traditional university course exam that uses pens, papers and invigilators. Online Exam can improve the standards of Student's examination whereas the traditional examination system using the pen and paper requires more effort on the part of students and invigilators.

Online Examinations are considered an important source for university exam, and the development of network technology policies has given the possibility to conduct the exam online. Thus the university student can benefit from these services.

- The maximum amount of question,
 - the minimum amount of question,
 - The largest difficulty score difference
- to let us consider the swinging has slowed down,
- The number of question (usually calculated as a function of standard deviation) needed to be asked to students to finish the test after the slowdown of the swinging (within the same swinging),
 - The interpolation strategy followed after the algorithm stopped (directly related to the threshold specified).

4. There must be sufficient amount of questions (on the same difficulty level) prepared to reduce the probability to face the same question to the acceptable level.

Analysis of system requirements

System requirements were analyzed by assessing the system framework, the basic functional modules, and technical points. The online assessment system was built on B/S (Browser/Server) model and operated on an MS

platform following the principles of integrity, standardization, scalability, and security. The whole system was data compatible and expandable.

2. Construction of question bank

An expert group was put in place to regularly classify, proof-read, and update all questions. The question bank covered a wide range of question on basic nursing, medical nursing, surgical nursing, obstetrics, gynaecological nursing, and pediatric nursing. Questions were formed as type A, type B, type X, multiple choice, true/false, fill-in-the-blank, short answer, essay, and one case study question.

Three types of tests were assembled for this study:

1. Paper tests: We collected a random sampling of test questions, but specified question topics, difficulty, and question format. Three versions of paper tests were randomly distributed to the examinees. Each test version had identical content, but questions were in different orders.

2. Online tests: A testing Centre was created in a way to prevent cheating. The online test system could track examinees' responses in real-time, track progress, compute current accuracy, and generate scores. The system was also configured with power failure backups, anti-crash technology, and an alert when five minutes were remaining.

3. Mock tests: The online system also provided mock tests for training purposes.

Management of tests

The testing systems required the following managerial upkeep:

1. Question bank management: Questions were organized categorically in a tree-like structure. The system could customize the question topic, format, and difficulty of questions. It could also accept bulk importing, error location, and similarity check.

2. Paper test management: The system was designed with the ability to print,

reorganize, modify, review, and evaluate all paper tests.

3. Examination management: The system had the capability to set the examination environment, preventing cheating, security assurance, and enter simulation mode.

4. Score management: Qualified professionals assessed subjective questions, while objective scores were automatically marked correct or incorrect. Test scores were calculated by statistical functions. Results were exported and archived into 20 statistical reports for further utilization.

5. User management: The system could set, modify, and store users' information.

3. Examination methods

The experimental group was tested via the online assessment system. Prior to testing, a short training was carried out to ensure that participants knew how to take the exam. The ¹¹²³⁴¹⁵control group was tested using paper tests. Questions included the standard examination syllabus from

4. SCOPE

Online Examination arrangement is a Multiple Choice Questions based Examination framework. It gives a simple way to utilize the environment for both test-conductors and understudies showing up for examination. Online Examination System is a web application that sets up a system between the establishments and understudies. Establishments enter on the site the inquiries they need in the exam. These inquiries are shown as a test to the qualified understudies. The answers enter by the understudies are then assessed what's more, their score is computed and spared. This score then can be got to by the organizations to focus the passes understudies or to assess their execution. Online Examination System gives the stage yet does not specifically take an interest in, nor is it included in any tests led. Inquiries are posted not by the site, but rather clients of the site. The site requires an organization to enlist before posting the

inquiries. The site has a manager who watches out for the general working of the framework.

- To permit workforce to give extra time to understudies with handicaps.
- To permit workforce to make tests and answer key.
- To permit programmed reviewing and manual evaluating which can be recorded per test.

To find out the most preferred student-teacher communication method from students' perspectives.⁶

5.Objective

- The main objective of this online exam system is to reduce the work of conducting the exam.
- The online examination system is a web based application which is useful all over the educational and corporate sector.

This online examination system includes the architectural components as Browser-Server architecture, Client-Server Architecture, Auto Question Generator System, Security, Randomization.

The Random Number Generator Algorithm is used for this system. It is described forward.

6.LITERATURE REVIEW

The online collaborative learning environment was found to have significant influence upon students' learning Achievements. The majority of the students improved in performance tests by being able to step up a level above the previous stage. In fact, some of the students performed very well in performance tests by being able to move directly from the low-achiever level to the high-achiever level. This finding confirms the hypothesis that students can perform significantly better upon learning in online collaborative learning environment, and is in line with other previous findings

UML DIAGRAM

7. METHODOLOGY

The project (Online Examination System) is developed by using:-

FRONT-END:- PHP(Hypertext Preprocessor)

BACK-END:- MySQL

Introduction to Php: PHP, which stands for "PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor", is an HTML-embedded scripting language. Much of its syntax is borrowed from C, Java and Perl with a couple of unique PHP-specific features thrown in. The goal of the language is to allow web developers to write dynamically generated pages quickly.

Example 1.1 An introductory example

```
<html>
<head>
<title>Example</title>
</head>
<body>
<?php
echo "Hi, I'm a PHP script!";
?>
</body>
</html>
```

Introduction to Mysql: MYSQL is a

high performance, relational database server based on MYSQL. It is built on CLIENT/SERVER architecture, which means a frontend or client component, and a back end, or server component. MySQL serverforms the back-end component in this architecture and is responsible for providing allthe standard DBMS functions. The client component, for which there are many different possibilities, is responsible for providing all of the user interface and application-processing function. The language usedto communicate between clients and database.

JavaScript:

Java script is embedded into HTML documents and is executed with in them. Java script is browser dependent.JavaScript is an interpreted language that can be interpreted by the browser at run time. Java script is loosely typed language. Java script is an object-based language.Java script is an Event-Driven language and supports event handlers to specify the functionality of a button.JavaScript is a high-level, dynamic, untyped, and interpreted programming language. It has been standardized in the ECMAScript language specification.

Example An introductory example

```
var sum = function() {
    var i, x = 0;
    for (i = 0; i < arguments.length; ++i) {
        x += arguments[i];
    }
    return x;
}
sum(1, 2, 3); // returns 6
```

CSS

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is a style sheet language used for describing the presentation of a document written in a markup language. Although most often used to set the visual style of web pages and user interfaces written in HTML and XHTML, the language can be applied to any XML document, including plain XML, SVG and XUL, and is applicable to

rendering in speech, or on other media. Along with HTML and JavaScript, CSS is a cornerstone technology used by most websites to create visually engaging webpages, user interfaces for web applications, and user interfaces for many mobile applications.

MODULES:

The system after careful analysis has been identified to be presented with the following modules and roles. The modules involved are:

1. Administrator
2. Users⁷

8.SYSTEM ANALYSIS

In the system analysis phase the proposed system is defined. In some cases the project management may decide to develop a prototype of the system to demonstrate the understanding of the user requirements and the functionality that will be provided in the proposed system. Structured analysis is the blueprint of a computer system solution to a problem. Or we can say that Structured analysis is the activity of deriving a structured model of the requirements of a system.

Feasibility study is test of a system proposal according to its workability, impact on the organization, ability to meet user needs and effective use of resources. All the projects are feasible given unlimited resources and infinite time! Ergo, feasibility study means an evaluation of benefits versus costs incurred in developing project, where cost includes manpower, time, resources and money.

A purpose of feasibility study is to check out the possibility of a computerized solution to the organization's observed problem before very much money that has been spent on.

A feasibility study is carried out to select the best system that meets performance requirements. Only by spending the time to evaluate the feasibility do I reduce the chances for extreme embarrassment at later stage of the system project.

TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY :-

Technical analysis evaluates technical merits of the system at the same time collecting additional information about performance, reliability, maintainability and productivity. In some cases, this system analysis step also includes a limited amount of research and design.

The proposed system has system capacity of required to hold data. This project is efficient and responds quickly for various enquires regardless of number of locations. The system proposed should be expanded easily and efficiency, whenever required.

Requirement	How Accomplished?
Front end	HTML, DHTML, JavaScript
Back end	MySQL
Technology used	PHP
Server	Apache
Documentation Tools	Macromedia Dream weaver MX, Edit plus, Microsoft FrontPage
Communication Tools	Intranet/Internet

9.THREATS TO SYSTEM SECURITY

A procedure for protecting systems makes sure that the facility is physically secure, provides a recovery/restart capability, and has access to backup files. If we list in order of probability the threats to system security or data integrity, research shows that the most damage comes from errors and omissions-people making mistakes. The threat of external attack on a computer system is virtually last. This means that in establishing a priority sequence, one

would probably want to start from within the firm and workout. The list of potential threats is:

- I. Errors and omissions.
- II. Disgruntled and dishonest employees.
- III. Fire
- IV. Natural Disasters
- V. External attack

10. Conclusions

With the use of this system, we can moderately conclude that: It can help the authorization of the educational institution to maintain the safety and integrity of its important data like record of attendance, exam results, etc. as the data shall instantly be transmitted on the cloud wireless. The authorities not need to worry about misplacement pervert of attendance registers or exam registers, etc. In case of network failure, the client agent and server tolerates it according to which phase this failure is occurred. If a network connection failure is occurred during the client agent sending the student's username⁸ and password and the login information lost. In further studies, practicability, validity, reliability, advantages and disadvantages of adaptive exam systems will be discussed through the statistical analyses over data that will be obtained as a result of the future adaptive exam system application⁹. Information integration is the technical term for digital in- formation collection, storage, classification, analysis, and sharing. Such practices allow for system standardization, which is the foundation of modern management practices.¹

REFERENCE

1. Cui JR, Chen Y, Zhang HY. Development and application of an online testing system for clinical nurses. *Int J Nurs Sci*. 2015;2(3):313-316. doi:10.1016/j.ijnss.2015.07.005
2. Shukor NA, Tasir Z, Van der Meijden H. An Examination of Online Learning Effectiveness Using Data Mining. *Procedia - Soc Behav Sci*. 2015;172:555-562. doi:10.1016/

j.sbspro.2015.01.402

3. Arikan A. An examination of online grammar teaching materials available for young learners. *Procedia - Soc Behav Sci*. 2014;158:18-22. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.12.026

4. Eriksson N, Rosenbröijer CJ, Fagerström A. The relationship between young consumers' decision-making styles and propensity to shop clothing online with a smartphone. *Procedia Comput Sci*. 2017;121:519-524. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2017.11.069

5. Diéguez-Soto J, Fernández-Gámez MA, Sánchez-Marín G. Family involvement and hotel online reputation. *BRQ Bus Res Q*. 2017;20(3):151-163. doi:10.1016/j.brq.2017.05.001

6. Almaghaslah D, Ghazwani M, Alsayari A, Khaled A. Pharmacy students' perceptions towards online learning in a Saudi Pharmacy School. *Saudi Pharm J*. 2018:1-5. doi:10.1016/j.jsps.2018.03.001

7. Chittil S, Chittil N, M R R. Online Shopping System. *Div Comput Sci*. 2014;(March):1-31.

8. Younis MI, Hussein MS. Construction of an Online Examination System with Resumption and Randomization Capabilities. 4(2):62-82.

9. Ya M, Ünal M. Designing and implementing an adaptive online examination system. 2014;116:3079-3083. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.711

10. Bobde S. Web Based Online Examination System. *Glob Res Dev J Eng*. 2017;2(5):58-61.

Other References

1. Title:- "Laptop Distribution Among Engineering graduate students in Chhattisgarh: A Brief Perspective" Page No.- 050-054, Vol.- 01 ISSUE- 31 Month – July Year- 2017

2. Title:- "Analyzing Laptop Distribution and Effects Among Engineering students in Chhattisgarh:" Page No.- 027-035, Vol.- 02 ISSUE-

19 Month – June Year- 2017

3. Title:- “A Study of network Attacks and Features of Secure Protocols” Page No.- 1-3, Vol.- 08 ISSUE- 1 Month – March Year- 2017

4. Title:- “Enhanced Data Security in Network Environment” Page No.- 396-405, Vol.- 14 ISSUE- 04 Month – April Year- 2016

5. Title:- “A Study of web portal features as a knowledge management in school education” Page No.- 1-4, Vol.- 05 ISSUE- 5 Month – Feb Year- 2016

6. Title:- “A Study of Security Mechanisms Implemented in Network Protocols” Page No.- 1-3, Vol.- 05 ISSUE- 11 Month – December Year- 2015

7. Title:- “Network Security Mechanisms Through OSI/ISO Network Model for Upper Layers” Page No.- 1-4, Vol.- 05 ISSUE- 6 Month – December Year- 2015

8. Title:- “Developing and analyzing portal Based Knowledge management solution” Page No.- 0143-0147, Vol.- 02 ISSUE- 8 Month – October Year- 2014

9. Title:- “Nutritional importance and health benefits of Mushroom for women and Overview” Page No.- 0143-0147, Vol.- 03 ISSUE- 1 Month – March Year- 2013

10. Title:- “A Impact of ICT enabled Distance Learning models on learners performance” Page No.- 79-86, Vol.- 05 ISSUE- 02 Month – July-December Year- 2012

11. Title:- “Impact of Web Enabled knowledge platform: An Analysis” Page No.- 1-7, Vol.- 04 ISSUE- 1 Month – June Year- 2012

12. Title:- “APQN Beyond first decade of 21 century” Page No.- 16-19, Vol.- 15 ISSUE- 04 Month – January Year- 2012

13. Title:- “Measuring effectiveness of ICT tools teaching school children: A Case study from Chhattisgarh state , India” Page No.- 29-34, Vol.- 06 ISSUE- 3 Month – December Year- 2010

